

Additional File 8. Tr1 cell sorting gating strategy

Tr1 cells were sorted from thawed PBMC. Gating strategy is shown: from singlets (FSC-A, FSC-H), to lymphocytes (FSC, SSC), live cells (SSC, 7AAD⁻), T cells (SSC, CD3⁺), memory CD4⁺ T cells (CD4⁺CD45RA⁻), and Tr1 cells (CD49b⁺LAG3⁺).